

Assembly Bowing Reactivity Calculation Methodology Applied to Lead Fast Reactor

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ABSTRACT

Ducted assemblies bow during operation due to power and temperature gradients which can be influenced by operating flow rates. For fast spectrum cores using ducted assemblies, the bowing behavior follows that of the duct and because there are gaps between the ducts, the bowing can result in compaction or expansion of the active core. This local displacement can have a positive or negative impact and knowing the net effect during transients is important for system reactivity control. Keeping the net bowing reactivity worth low is possible with attentive placement of load pads above the active core and selecting load pad gap thicknesses that result in a desired behavior at standard operating conditions. This paper considers a Lead Fast Reactor (LFR) concept fueled by HALEU UO₂ developed by Westinghouse Electric Company (WEC) and applies a workflow of Argonne-developed codes to estimate the core bowing reactivity worth. Using orifice flow rates grouped by assembly type, the net reactivity impact due to core assembly bowing for the LFR was found to be small and in line with other liquid metal fast reactors: +29/+32/+35 pcm, or about +\$0.049/+\$0.055/+\$0.059, for BOEC/MOEC/EOEC, respectively.

Keywords. LFR, bowing reactivity, PyARC

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper focuses on bowing reactivity worth calculation methodology and how it is applied to fast spectrum systems. Typically, fast-spectrum assemblies have ducts to control the flow rate in each assembly (reflector, control, shield assemblies produce less power than driver assemblies). When a reactor core is brought from a cold shutdown state to full power, the change in temperatures in the system results in thermal expansion of the ducted assemblies. The bowing displacement is dominated by the temperature distribution on the duct wall. Assemblies can experience differential thermal expansion along each duct face due to power gradients across the assembly and between assemblies (inter-assembly heat transfer). This creates a temperature gradient across each duct where a hotter side expands more than a relatively colder side (typical gradient of interest is when this occurs on opposite sides of a given assembly). Due to the nature of fuel assemblies being relatively tall, slender members, they are subject to non-negligible displacements from the combination of temperature gradients and applied forces referred to as bowing. The duct temperature gradient dictates both the direction and magnitude of the resulting assembly bowing.

Bowing can have an impact on core reactivity, and the typical design goal is to ensure it does not result in positive reactivity feedback in transients where duct temperatures increase. In conventional fast

spectrum reactor design, assembly bowing that yields negative net reactivity feedback is achieved by proper placement of load pads above the fueled portion of the core toward the top of the assemblies and adequate size of the gap separating them [1]. This includes both the Top Load Pad (TLP) and Above Core Load Pad (ACLP). This design approach comes with some additional assurances that the residual forces applied to each assembly are low enough that the assemblies can be withdrawn from the core post-irradiation. Overall, modeling assembly bowing is important for reactor safety. The current state-of-the-art high-fidelity approach is to use modeling and analysis software from the Nuclear Energy Advanced Modeling and Simulation (NEAMS) program's MOOSE [2] suite. The mechanics predictions coming from MOOSE's thermo-mechanical models are consistent with conventional structural mechanics calculation methods and are detailed further in [3]. Validation efforts of bowing reactivity effects have been conducted on experimental reactors [4], with more planned in coming years.

In recent work performed at Argonne National Laboratory (ANL), bowing reactivity worth analysis was accomplished by using the set of lower fidelity ARC (Argonne Reactor Computation) codes, as outlined in Figure 1. In this framework, the core neutron and gamma power distributions are obtained using DIF3D [5] [6] and GAMSOR [7]. Given the spatial power distribution, a steady state temperature distribution is obtained using DASSH [8] [9]. The resulting duct temperatures are used by NUBOW-3D [10] to assess the mechanical performance noting that the fast flux spatial distribution from DIF3D is included to account for irradiation induced creep and swelling. The geometric displacements predicted by NUBOW-3D at various time points are then passed to PERSENT [11] [12] which calculates the reactivity worth of the various bowed states (without taking into account additional density changes). This methodology has already been successfully applied to a sodium fast reactor system [13], and in this paper it is applied to a lead fast reactor (LFR) designed by Westinghouse Electric Company (WEC).

Figure 1. Modeling approach developed to estimate core bowing reactivity worth.

2. LFR DESIGN DESCRIPTION

The core bowing analysis performed in this paper is based on the LFR core configuration described in [14]. It utilizes the limited free bow core restraint concept [1], which has been used in FFTF [15] among others. The design assumes High-Assay Low Enriched Uranium (HALEU) UO_2 fuel.

The radial layout of the LFR core is shown in Figure 2 noting that it has a 120-degree periodic layout. The key core characteristics are shown in Table I. This is a 950 MWt core with an active core effective diameter of about 2.8 m and about 1.5 m in height. It uses four radial enrichment zones labeled "Inner Fuel", "Middle Fuel", "Outer Fuel" and "External Fuel" in Figure 2. The control and safety rod configurations consist of nine control assemblies each. There are several rings of lead coolant reflector

assemblies surrounding the active core interior to the ring of shield assemblies which serve as a simplified treatment for the radial reflector that would be used for the core. Detailed descriptions of fuel and control rod assemblies, together with material compositions are provided in [14].

Figure 2. Radial layout of the LFR.

Table 1. LFR core summary parameters.

Nominal Core Thermal Power (MWt)	950
Fuel Assemblies (#)	247
Control and Safety Assemblies (#)	18 (9/9)
Modeled Assembly Height (m)	3.631
ACLP Loc. (m) / Gap Thickness (mm)*	2.996 / 0.2
TLP Loc. (m) / Gap Thickness (mm)*	3.56 / 0.4

*The placement and gap thicknesses for both the ACLP and TLP were selected for this work based on the core temperature field and resulting bowing behavior. These assumed values have not been used nor optimized in previous analyses.

3. METHODOLOGIES DESCRIPTION

The following section provides an overview of the ARC tools used for bowing reactivity analysis. Each component is used to model different phenomena, with their combined physics capturing the effect of core bowing.

3.1. DIF3D / GAMSOR

The core power distribution in the LFR is solved by using DIF3D and GAMSOR. DIF3D [5] is a 3D deterministic solver of the neutral particle diffusion (and transport) equation and is based upon an assembly homogenized model. For all of this work, the DIF3D-VARIANT [6] option is used which is the even-parity P_N transport solver in DIF3D. The neutronics solution obtained with DIF3D is separated into neutron and gamma power distributions via GAMSOR [7]. These resolved spatial power distributions are passed to DASSH which obtains the steady state temperature distribution in the domain.

3.2. DASSH

DASSH is a subchannel thermal analysis code that finds temperature distributions resolved to the pin and coolant subchannel level. DASSH originated as a Python-based successor [8] to older subchannel thermal analysis codes used at ANL, but was rewritten in Fortran to have better computational performance [9]. Using the spatial power and neutronic output from GAMSOR, DASSH solves the temperature distribution over the entire domain. One aspect that is challenging for the design work here is that the in-vessel storage assemblies are modeled as empty hex cans. This means that the true power deposited in those assemblies would be far higher if they were occupied with previously irradiated assemblies than what the current model assumes. Thus, the assumed flow rates in this work lead to lower than expected temperature gradients in those assembly regions as will be shown later. The duct wall temperature distribution as well as the fast flux distribution is passed to NUBOW-3D.

3.3. NUBOW-3D

NUBOW-3D is a code that calculates the displacements of assemblies due to thermal expansion and contact with the core restraint system [10]. It also includes the time-dependent effects of neutron fluence and internal stresses to estimate irradiation-induced swelling and creep for structural components. NUBOW-3D uses the temperature distribution from DASSH to obtain the temperature gradient across each assembly to calculate the displacement of each assembly along its axial length. The assembly displacement field is passed to PERSENT which computes the reactivity worth of the geometric movement.

3.4. PERSENT

PERSENT is a perturbation and sensitivity capability intended for fast-spectrum systems for homogenized assembly models [11] [12]. As mentioned, both DIF3D and PERSENT assume an assembly homogenized methodology. To capture the worth of the geometric movement PERSENT assumes a two region model as shown in Figure 3 (greatly exaggerated gap). As seen, the bypass gap coolant region around the assembly is explicitly represented while everything internal to the duct is homogenized. Given the geometric displacement information, PERSENT uses the flux solution from DIF3D for the fully homogenized assembly model to evaluate a first order perturbation theory operator that includes the two-region model shown in Figure 3 (base and perturbed states thereof). This approach yields a spatial distribution of reactivity worth and is further detailed and verified in [16].

Figure 3. Two-region geometric representation of bowing ducts in PERSENT.

4. RESULTS FOR LFR BOWING ANALYSIS

This section details the results of running the ARC codes to estimate the bowing reactivity worth of the LFR. Important findings and results passed between codes are detailed here, mostly focusing on the Beginning of Equilibrium Cycle (BOEC) results for brevity.

4.1. DIF3D Neutronics Results

Equilibrium fuel cycle analysis was obtained using the fuel cycle analysis solver REBUS [17] with follow-on neutronics results coming from DIF3D-VARIANT and GAMSOR at each time step. The axially-integrated BOEC power (accounting for both neutron and gamma heating) for each assembly location, including empty lead-filled locations, are shown in Figure 4 (left). The power distribution provided to DASSH from DIF3D/GAMSOR contains a full spatial distribution within each DIF3D mesh (axial segment of each assembly).

4.2. DASSH Thermal Hydraulic Results

The core temperature distribution was solved using DASSH with the neutron and gamma power results coming from DIF3D/GAMSOR. DASSH takes the homogenized power distribution and uses full heterogeneous assembly geometry to determine the power distribution in the pins, ducts, and coolant regions of each assembly. It uses that power distribution to calculate the temperature distribution in all modeled components of the core. DASSH assumed an inlet temperature of 390 °C with a coolant flow rate through the core prescribed by assembly type, summarized in Table II. The target outlet temperature of the core is 645 °C. The resulting bulk coolant outlet temperature for each assembly is shown in Figure 4 (right). The coolant outlet temperature in the lead-filled reflector region is considerably lower than the desired 645 °C because the current preliminary model assumes very little power is deposited as seen in Figure 4 (left). A better flow rate for the reflector region will be implemented in future efforts when a more detailed design of the reflector region is available.

Figure 4. Left: BOEC axially integrated assembly power [MW thermal]. Right: BOEC temperature distribution [°C].

Table II. Summary of lead coolant flow rate through each assembly.

Assembly Type	Flow Rate [kg/s]
Inner Fuel	119.2
Middle Fuel	117.3
Outer Fuel	100.0
External Fuel	81.5
Control / Safety Rod	5.4
Empty (Lead-filled)	0.5
Shield	0.5

4.3. NUBOW-3D Bowing Results

Using the temperature results from DASSH, NUBOW-3D was used to calculate the bowing for each assembly location at several time points. Recall that this is mostly dictated by the temperature gradient across the outer duct for each assembly. The bowing behavior is displayed in Figure 5 (left) for a 120-degree section of the core model isolating just the first ten rings (fueled portion). It shows the movement (cm) to/from the center of the domain (radial movement) with a greatly exaggerated visual geometric displacement. Included in Figure 5 (right) is a profile view of the first assembly position in each ring. The assembly numbers in Figure 5 (right) correspond to the row of assemblies starting with the central assembly (1), going through the control assembly in the fourth ring (20) and ending with a shield assembly (548). As seen, there are fifteen rings: ten with fuel, four with lead coolant, and one outermost ring with shield assemblies. The horizontal lines around 130 cm and 280 cm denote the bottom and top of the active core region, respectively. From Figure 5, one can discern a wide range of bowing in each assembly where there is clearly compaction occurring above the midpoint of each assembly. The assemblies adjacent to the control assembly located in the fourth ring have higher gradients than the other interior fuel assemblies. Since the higher temperatures occur on the faces away from the control assemblies, the assemblies bow away from the control assemblies. There is relatively little bowing in the inner enrichment region of the core compared with the outer and external enrichment regions, due to the smaller temperature gradients. This results in core compaction (anticipated and common for fast-spectrum systems) and the reactivity impact is expected to be slightly positive from such bowing.

*Figure 5. Left: BOEC bowing behavior in first ten rings of assemblies.
Right: BOEC assembly bowing moving radially outward.*

4.4. PERSENT Bowing Reactivity Results

The assembly-wise bowing results from NUBOW-3D were used to construct a PERSENT input where each homogenized assembly location is displaced in the corresponding direction conceptually similar to what is shown in Figure 3. The total calculated reactivity worth of core bowing is: +29/+32/+35 pcm ($\$/0.049/\$/0.055/\$/0.059$) for BOEC/MOEC/EOEC respectively. A visualization of the spatial reactivity

distribution at BOEC is provided in Figure 6. The two pictures provided only show the worth distribution over the inner ten rings (the fuel assemblies) as the outer five rings had significantly lower worth (~ 2 orders of magnitude less than that shown). The left picture shows the full axial height which includes large sections that contribute very little to the worth (gray coloring). The right picture strips away these low worth sections and shows the high positive and negative worth which make up a vast majority of the total worth. This section should also be recognized as the active core region in the axial range. There are significant positive contributions coming from the compaction of the fuel assemblies at the upper part of the active core region. The negative worth regions of the domain correspond to those assemblies in the middle enrichment region which are pushed outward from the core center. The compaction of the outer enrichment assemblies is larger than the negative worth associated with the middle enrichment assemblies bowing out, resulting in the net positive bowing reactivity worth.

Figure 6. Bowing reactivity worth distribution (first ten rings only). Units shown are for local contribution to change in k_{eff} .

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a methodology for computing the bowing reactivity worth, and its application to an LFR. The displayed workflow using ANL-developed ARC codes was applied to an LFR, starting with using REBUS to compute the equilibrium fuel cycle behavior of the system. At each time point, the spatial distribution of power (neutron and gamma) is calculated with DIF3D and GAMSOR. Those power distributions are then passed to DASSH which calculates the core temperature profile and fast neutron flux. The temperature and fast flux distributions are passed to NUBOW-3D which calculates the bowing direction and magnitude for each assembly. The geometric displacement field is passed to PERSENT which calculates the reactivity worth. The reactivity impact of bowing between zero and full power is a small positive effect (29/32/35 pcm, \$0.049/\$0.055/\$0.059). These positive reactivity bowing values are common for fast-spectrum metal-fueled reactors (like EBR-II [18]) and are not concerning in themselves since they are small relative to other feedback coefficients (such as Doppler and axial expansion). Further work would involve using another modeling suite like the appropriate NEAMS/MOOSE tools to verify the results found in this work.

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